

Training for Forest Operators in Intervention Techniques to Enhance Carbon Credit Generation

Introduction

A project aimed at generating ecosystem credits requires approval from a verification body. Among all the criteria necessary for project approval, additionality is perhaps the key factor: it must be demonstrated that without the implementation of the project and specific management measures, no environmental benefit would be achieved. Therefore, in the context of ecosystem credit generation, it is necessary to develop additionality projects through silvicultural interventions that increase carbon storage and improve biodiversity within the canopy. These silvicultural interventions, as opposed to conventional forestry practices, require specific training for the operators working in the forest.

Within the framework of OG CO2S.Fo.Ma, which has the goal of enhancing carbon credits, it was considered important to provide specific training for forestry operators in silvicultural choices and forest interventions aimed at generating additionality. The training included activities such as selective harvesting, thinning, conversion to high forest, and the selection of trees to promote biodiversity aspects. The training was conducted directly in the forest through a practical course. The training allowed for practical activities to explain how to carry out additionality projects and to educate operators who typically work in the forest only on conventional silvicultural interventions. This has enabled the operators to become self-sufficient in implementing specific additionality interventions in the designated OG CO2S.Fo.Ma project area, as well as to make them self-sufficient for future additionality projects in other areas.

Lessons learned

The course was useful for pursuing qualitative growth in the work of forestry workers with a view to sustainable forest management and the improvement of ecosystem services and the carbon stock. The practical course was considered useful by the operators because it was conducted directly in the forest. Furthermore, it allowed for the expansion of the operators' skills.

For further information contact

Marco Perrino, Project Coordinator, Italy, email: marco.perrino@dream-italia.net

Francesca Giannetti, Assistant Professor, University of Florence, Italy, e-mail: francesca.giannetti@unifi.it

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://www.co2marche.it/>

--	---	--	--